

Original Article

Obtaining Sodium Aluminosilicate from Rice Husk

Nurbol O. Appazov¹, Meruyert Tolegenkyzy¹, Guldina E. Shudabay², Anel Serikkul³, Neeraj Kumar⁴, Sergiy Lyubchyk⁴, Ziyada Zh. Appazova³, Marat I. Syzdykbayev¹, Nurlybek A. Akhatayev¹, Esenzhol A. Nazarov^{1,*}, Bakytbek B. Abzhalelov^{1,*}, Gulzat Sh. Askarova¹, Assylkhan A. Shomantayev¹, Guldana S. Dairbekova⁴, Artem L. Gushchin⁵, Indira D. Yespanova¹, Dinara Zh. Niyazova¹, Rakhymzhan A. Turmanov¹, Rakhmetulla U. Zhapparbergenov¹, Roza A. Narmanova¹

¹Laboratory of Engineering Profile, Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University, Kyzylorda, Kazakhstan

²"Syr-Aral Expertise" LLP, Kyzylorda, Kazakhstan

³Department of Metal Forming, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

⁴Deep Technology Laboratory, Universidade Lusofona, Lisboa, Portugal

⁵Laboratory of Chemistry of Complex Compounds, Nikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry SB RAS, Novosibirsk, Russia

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ABSTRACT

This work addresses the processing of large-scale agricultural waste – rice husk, which is utilized as a source of silicon for the synthesis of sodium aluminosilicate. A method for producing sorbents, in particular an aluminosilicate adsorbent for the purification of natural and wastewater in various industrial sectors, is described. As a result of mixing 50 mL of a saturated aluminum sulfate solution with sodium silicate (obtained by microwave irradiation of a mixture of 130 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide solution with 10 g of ground, distilled water-washed, and air-dried rice husk), a precipitate is formed. Subsequent thermal treatment of this precipitate at different temperatures yields sorbents with varying sorption characteristics. This method of producing sodium aluminosilicate from rice husk is efficient and environmentally sustainable, enabling the utilization of agricultural waste while obtaining valuable adsorbents with high performance.

* Corresponding author: Esenzhol A. Nazarov, Bakytbek B. Abzhalelov

E-mail: nazarov_e@korkyt.kz, bakhytbek@korkyt.kz

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Introduction

Rice is one of the most important food crops and the primary source of carbohydrates in the human diet. However, its processing generates a significant amount of by-product – rice husk (up to 20% of the rice mass). The annual global output of this waste is estimated at approximately 200 million tons [1,2], which makes it an important renewable resource. Due to the presence of about 20% silica and 30-50% organic carbon (cellulose and lignin) in its composition [3], rice husk is resistant to biodegradation and is considered as a promising raw material for adsorbent production.

The use of rice husks as fuel for industrial boilers is limited by their low calorific value, high moisture content, and substantial collection and transportation costs. In tire and cement manufacturing, primarily the silica contained in the husks is utilized, while the organic fraction remains underexploited. Open-field burning of husks releases carbon monoxide, volatile organic compounds, and carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, which negatively affect both the environment and human health [4,5].

Therefore, the efficient utilization of rice husk is a pressing task for all countries engaged in rice cultivation and processing.

Publications [6-15] provide examples of their application in the production of silica, activated carbon, biochar, and cellulose.

Aluminosilicates represent an interconnected network of aluminates and silicates, possessing both intermolecular and intramolecular porosity, which enables their application in areas such as adsorption, catalysis, pyrolysis, and beyond. They maintain the significance of their current uses while also opening opportunities for new

applications in chemical processes and separation technologies. The phase composition and properties of aluminosilicates depend on the specific synthesis methods employed [16].

Aluminosilicates stand out among other classes of inorganic compounds and are of particular interest due to the diversity of their functional properties, which depend both on structure and on chemical composition, the latter varying within a wide range [17,18]. The most significant drawbacks of natural silicates are their low specific surface area and the variability of chemical and phase composition, even within a single deposit. In contrast, synthetic aluminosilicates surpass natural analogues in several respects, offering consistent composition and the absence of impurities. At the same time, the chemical and phase composition of synthetic aluminosilicates is largely determined by the synthesis method and the raw materials employed [18,19].

In this regard, particular attention is drawn to agricultural waste from silicon-accumulating crops, such as rice, as a silicon-containing feedstock. The problem of agricultural waste generation and disposal is acute worldwide, with the primary method of utilization being combustion [19,20]. This process results in ash composed mainly of silicon dioxide of varying degrees of purity. However, the possibility of obtaining aluminosilicates from plant-based raw materials remains relatively underexplored, despite their potential advantages over silica, for example, when used as selective sorbents [18,21]. Both natural and synthetic aluminosilicates are primarily applied as various sorbents, catalyst supports, and ion-exchange materials [22,23]. The separation of vapors and gases, in which aluminosilicates are widely used, is an important

process in many branches of the chemical industry [16]. They are also incorporated into animal feed contaminated with aflatoxins, providing a protective effect against the development of aflatoxicosis in livestock [24]. Additionally, a composite of sodium aluminosilicate and $\text{NaZr}_2\text{Si}_2\text{PO}_{12}$ has been employed as a solid-state electrochemical sensor for CO_2 gas [16].

An essential characteristic of aluminosilicates is their acid–base properties, which reflect nearly all fundamental parameters and functional features of solid substances. Knowledge of the composition and content of active sites makes it possible to predict the reactivity and sorption capacity of the surface with respect to pollutants of different nature (such as heavy metal ions and organic dyes) [18].

Currently, researchers are actively developing environmentally friendly and resource-saving methods of rice husk processing aimed at obtaining products of industrial significance. Publications [22-31] provide examples of their application for the synthesis of adsorbents.

It has also been demonstrated that nanostructured X-ray amorphous sodium aluminosilicate with a specific surface area of $364 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ can be obtained using an alkaline hydrolysate of rice straw [2]. Furthermore, a method has been reported for the synthesis of nanostructured sodium aluminosilicates with a Si/Al ratio ranging from 1 to 5 in a multicomponent aqueous system. Data have been presented on the elemental composition, morphology, thermal behavior of the synthesized compounds, and their sorption activity toward Cs^+ ions under static conditions [32].

Experimental

The objective of this study was to develop a method for producing an adsorbent based on sodium aluminosilicate for the purification of natural and wastewater. The technical approach involved mixing 50 mL of a saturated aluminum sulfate solution with sodium silicate (obtained by microwave irradiation of a mixture of 130 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide solution with 10 g of

ground rice husk that had been washed with distilled water and dried to an air-dry state), resulting in the formation of a precipitate. Subsequent thermal treatment of this precipitate at different temperatures produced sorbents with varying sorption characteristics.

Rice husk was washed with distilled water and dried in a drying oven at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h. After drying, it was ground into a powder using a DKU "Optimus" grinding apparatus (Russia). A 10 g portion of the ground rice husk was mixed with 130 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide solution; the resulting mixture was treated in a microwave oven at 900 W with stirring for 10 min. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was vacuum-filtered through a Büchner funnel. The filtrate, containing sodium silicate solution, was reacted with 50 mL of saturated aluminum sulfate solution. The reaction proceeded instantaneously, yielding a light-brown sodium aluminosilicate precipitate.

The obtained aluminosilicate was vacuum-filtered on a Büchner funnel, washed with distilled water until a neutral reaction was achieved, and dried at room temperature to an air-dry state. Calcination was then carried out to determine the optimal conditions for sorbent production at temperatures ranging from 150 to $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h, with a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, using an STA-1800 muffle furnace (China). As a result, sorbent samples of different colors were obtained (Figure 1).

The adsorption activity of the obtained sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent from rice husk was evaluated using iodine adsorption capacity. The adsorption activity of the sorbent samples concerning iodine was determined in accordance with GOST 6217-74.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the synthesized sorbents was carried out using a Rigaku SmartLab SE diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 kV and 50 mA. The diffraction patterns were recorded over a 2θ range of 5° – 80° with a step size of 0.001° and a scanning rate of $2^\circ/\text{min}$.

Elemental composition analysis was performed using a Rigaku NEX GG X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (Japan). This method allowed

accurate determination of the content of various elements in the adsorbent, which is essential for assessing its structure and properties.

FTIR spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu IR-Prestige 21 spectrometer (Japan) in the range of 400–4,000 cm^{-1} without special sample preparation, employing a Smiths DuraSamplIR II

attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory with a single-reflection diamond/ZnSe prism (USA).

The surface morphology of the sorbent was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a JEOL JSM-6390LV microscope.

Figure 1: Ground adsorbent based on sodium aluminosilicate derived from rice husk

Results and Discussion

The study of the iodine adsorption activity of the sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent obtained from rice husk demonstrated that the material the iodine adsorption value reached a maximum of 81.2% at 700°C. Within the temperature range of 150-700 °C, the iodine adsorption activity

increased to 81.2%; however, at 750-800 °C, a decrease in iodine adsorption activity was observed. This property indicates its potential effectiveness for the purification of natural and wastewater, as well as other liquid media, from various pollutants. Experimental data on the iodine adsorption activity are presented in [Table 1](#).

Table 1: Iodine adsorption activity of sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent derived from rice husk

Temperature, °C	Adsorption activity, %
150	20.0
200	22.7
250	18.0
300	18.2
350	21.0
400	22.6
450	23.0
500	25.7
550	30.0
600	41.1
650	66.3
700	81.2
750	56.7
800	32.0

To study the crystalline structure of the obtained sorbents, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was carried out using a Rigaku SmartLab SE diffractometer with Cu K α radiation. The results demonstrated that the samples treated at different temperatures exhibited various aluminosilicate phases (Figure 2).

Aluminosilicate samples were analyzed at 150, 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650, and 700 °C (12 samples in total). The XRD patterns showed the presence of calcite (CaCO₃) only in the 150 °C sample. For all the other samples, the XRD patterns were dominated by amorphous humps (at 2 θ around = 20° to 30° for low temperatures) and weak crystalline peaks (for high temperatures) corresponding to the amorphous and low crystalline aluminosilicate gel. In the amorphous phases, there are no well-defined crystallographic planes (*i.e.*, there is no

long-range periodicity, only short-range order) to satisfy Bragg's law, so sharp diffraction peaks are absent. However, due to short-range order, there are still preferred interatomic distances. These give rise to broad, diffuse scattering maxima in the XRD pattern, often referred to as amorphous humps or halos [33-35].

The other peaks in the XRD patterns correspond to the poorly crystalline zeolitic phases: analcime, zeolite X (FAU-type framework), and zeolite A (LTA-type framework) corresponding to ICDD card numbers: 00-041-1478, 00-038-0237, and 00-043-0142 respectively, which are formed during the precipitation process. The intensities of these phases are not uniform with increase in temperature, resulting from the thermal instability of these phases. Some traces of quartz (SiO₂), and albite (NaAlSi₃O₈) were also observed [36,37].

Figure 2: Structural analysis of the samples performed by X-ray diffraction using a Rigaku SmartLab SE diffractometer

The elemental composition of sodium aluminosilicate adsorbents obtained from rice husk at different temperatures was analyzed. The elemental composition was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) using a NEX GG spectrometer (Rigaku, Japan). This method enabled the qualitative determination of the content of the main elements in the studied samples, which is

important for evaluating their structure and functional properties. The results are presented in Table 2.

The observed trends indicate that the temperature-induced compositional changes are non-uniform and are associated with several processes:

- Below 300 °C, the combustion of the organic

fraction and redistribution of alkali elements occur, which is confirmed by a sharp increase in Na₂O content.

- The range of 350-650 °C is characterized by the activation of aluminosilicate transformations, reflected in a noticeable increase in Al₂O₃ content.

- Above 650 °C, a relative stabilization of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ is observed, which may be attributed to the formation of thermodynamically stable phases.

Table 2: Elemental analysis of the obtained sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent

Temperature, °C	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃
150	56.80	10.60	1.45	0.255	0.154	0.022
200	57.20	10.90	1.38	0.284	0.157	0.027
250	59.40	11.50	4.63	0.918	0.363	0.069
300	56.00	9.75	8.40	0.166	0.125	0.014
350	57.20	15.00	1.01	0.235	0.184	0.033
400	57.30	8.82	2.38	0.449	0.249	0.013
450	55.70	9.60	7.17	0.471	0.201	0.035
500	56.20	11.60	6.76	0.133	0.051	0.022
550	55.90	12.30	4.15	0.268	0.029	0.047
600	56.10	14.80	2.92	0.287	0.223	0.054
650	56.10	19.60	2.19	0.218	0.188	0.063
700	58.20	18.90	2.14	0.219	0.198	0.062
750	56.20	17.50	2.17	0.213	0.189	0.056
800	55.40	9.50	7.15	0.456	0.201	0.035

Thus, based on the obtained data, it can be concluded that the optimal range for the stabilization of the ash structure lies between 600 and 700 °C, where the silica content reaches 56-58% and the aluminum content 15-19%. This promotes the formation of a more ordered aluminosilicate matrix.

In the FTIR spectra of the synthesized aluminosilicate sorbents, absorption bands corresponding to the bending vibrations of Si-O-Si were observed at 432 cm⁻¹, the symmetric stretching vibration of the SiO₄ unit at 578 cm⁻¹, Al-O-Si bond vibrations at 694 cm⁻¹, and stretching vibrations of Si-O in Si-O-Al bonds at 968 cm⁻¹. The FTIR spectra were identical for all

products. The spectrum of the adsorbent obtained at 700 °C was found to be optimal and is shown in [Figure 3](#).

Micrographs were obtained using a JSM-6510 LV scanning electron microscope (JEOL, Japan) and Axia ChemiSEM LoVac (Waltham, USA) using the SEM method, which is one of the most versatile tools for studying and analyzing the morphology and chemical composition of materials. The SEM images of the sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent derived from rice husk show that the obtained material possesses pores with diameters ranging from 0.1 to 1 μm. These data are presented in [Figure 4](#).

Figure 3: FTIR spectrum of sodium aluminosilicate obtained under optimal conditions

Figure 4: SEM micrograph of sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent derived from rice husk at 1500× magnification, obtained at 700 °C

Conclusion

The proposed method for obtaining sodium aluminosilicate from rice husk is both efficient and environmentally sustainable. It enables the utilization of agricultural waste and the production of valuable adsorbents with high performance characteristics. The method is simple to implement and can be optimized to obtain products with tailored properties. The study of iodine adsorption activity of the sodium aluminosilicate adsorbent derived from rice husk demonstrates that the material possesses a

significant capacity for iodine uptake from aqueous solutions. At 700 °C, the iodine adsorption activity increases to 81.2%.

Abbreviations

FTIR: Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
SEM: Scanning Electron Microscopy
IR: Infrared Spectroscopy
XRD: X-ray Diffraction

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ORCID

Nurbol O. Appazov

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8765-3386>

Meruyert Tolegenkyzy

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8916-9596>

Guldina E. Shudabay

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7131-5232>

Anel Serikkul

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2200-9182>

Neeraj Kumar

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5474-6893>

Sergiy Lyubchyk

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6323-9383>

Ziyada Zh. Appazova

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9378-4160>

Marat I. Syzdykbayev

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6069-4644>

Nurlybek A. Akhatayev

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8088-6072>

Esenzhol A. Nazarov

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2368-6466>

Bakytbek B. Abzhalelov

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5189-6762>

Gulzat Sh. Askarova

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0872-3161>

Assylkhan A. Shomantayev

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3089-8651>

Guldana S. Dairbekova

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1528-0637>

Artem L. Gushchin

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3214-1433>

Indira D. Yespanova

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0721-1794>

Dinara Zh. Niyazova

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2698-1209>

Rakhymzhan A. Turmanov

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7268-1699>

Rakhmetulla U. Zhapparbergenov

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0567-3226>

Roza A. Narmanova

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5672-7418>

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